

PERFORMANCE OF CODED FH/MFSK WITH A QUANTIZER-LIMITER IN A WORST-CASE PARTIAL BAND GAUSSIAN INTERFERENCE CHANNEL

Paul J. Crepeau

Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, D.C. 20375

ABSTRACT

The performance of coded FH/MFSK with a quantizer-limiter soft decision metric is presented for a worst-case two-level partial band Gaussian interference channel. This receiver structure is easy to implement and does not require side information concerning the on-off state of the interference. For a constraint length seven ($K = 7$), rate one-half ($R = 1/2$) convolutional code with Viterbi decoding, this receiver performs within 1.4 dB of the required E_b/N_0 at $P_b = 10^{-6}$ when compared to an ideal unquantized soft decision receiver assisted by perfect side information. The cutoff rate parameter R_0 is plotted versus channel symbol signal-to-noise ratio for alphabet sizes $M = 2, 4, 8, 16$, and 32.

INTRODUCTION

Modern digital communication systems are frequently required to operate in a variety of severe fading and jamming environments. These transmission channels are detrimental to all uncoded modulations, including noncoherent frequency hopped multiple frequency shift keying (FH/MFSK). Viterbi and Jacobs [1] showed in 1975 that for FH/MFSK a worst-case partial band Gaussian interference channel can change the dependence of bit-error probability P_b on signal-to-noise ratio (E_b/N_0) from an exponential dependence (for broadband Gaussian interference) to an inverse linear one. Viterbi and Jacobs showed also that the use of error control codes (either block or convolutional codes) can restore the exponential dependence of P_b on E_b/N_0 .

For a coded waveform, such as coded FH/MFSK, there are several options for providing the decoder with metric information. These are usually categorized as either hard or soft decision decoding. For broadband Gaussian interference, soft decision decoding invariably outperforms hard decision decoding. In contrast, for worst-case partial band Gaussian interference, there are special difficulties which must be addressed. Of particular concern is the fact that pure soft decision decoding (using analog demodulator energy outputs as decoder metrics) does not work effectively in an intelligent interference environment unless the decoder has side information concerning the state of the interference. Without side information a pure soft decision receiver is vulnerable to an interference strategy where high power can be concentrated on a small number of elements of a coded transmission sequence and cause a large number of decoding errors.

Interference state side information is an idealized concept for which there presently exists no practical realization. Implementation would require that the receiver assign an infinite metric to received symbols that have no interference. Viterbi and Jacobs [1] introduced this idealization, and it is the reason why they achieved large theoretical coding gains on the partial band Gaussian interference channel.

In contrast to pure soft decision decoding with side information, hard decision decoding (without side information) can be easily implemented, but there is a considerable loss in performance. For binary FSK and a constraint length $K = 7$, rate

$R = 1/2$ convolutional code (with Viterbi decoding), E_b/N_0 must be equal to 11.1 dB to achieve a value of P_b equal to 10^{-6} when soft decision decoding with side information is used. For hard decision decoding, the corresponding value of E_b/N_0 is 17.5 dB.

The goal of this paper is to analyze a soft decision scheme called the quantizer-limiter (Q-L) which provides performance close to that of a pure soft decision decoder with side information but allows for a practical implementation with simplicity close to that of a hard decision decoder. It achieves this dual purpose by taking the output of each of the M tone filters and quantizing it into N levels. The highest quantizer level provides a limit to the metric caused by interference so that interference strategies using high power levels are thwarted and side information is not required. On the other hand, the classification of filter outputs into N levels retains much of the channel reliability information needed for a high-performance soft decision receiver.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 is an overall diagram of the basic system elements. The channel encoder includes all of the important coding possibilities, either convolutional or block. Since MFSK signaling is assumed, the M -ary modulator accepts $\log_2 M$ channel bits and selects one of M orthogonal tones to represent a data block. This tone is pseudorandomly hopped in the frequency band at a rate of one hop per tone symbol. Higher or lower hopping rates are possible, but we restrict the analysis to this simple, but important, case.

The coded FH/MFSK signal is transmitted over the waveform channel. In this paper we consider the worst-case two-level partial band Gaussian interference channel. (Other partial band channels with multiple interference levels may be worse for the Q-L than the worst-case two-level channel; however, this question has not been investigated.) The two-level channel is characterized by additive Gaussian noise with flat spectral density N_0/ρ over a fraction ρ (where $0 < \rho \leq 1$) of the total hopping bandwidth and negligible interference over the remaining fraction $(1 - \rho)$ of the band. We assume that the M candidate tone slots in each subband are either all interfered with or they are all noise free. As a worst-case condition, we consider the situation where the parameter ρ is chosen so as to maximize the resulting probability of error.

On the receiver side, the signal is dehopped and sent to the MFSK demodulator. This device is composed of a bank of M filters, one matched to each of the M -ary orthogonal tones. The demodulator output is an M -dimensional vector whose elements are the M outputs of the filter bank. The M -vector output may be considered as a point in an M -dimensional output space of the demodulator. The role of the quantizer is to partition the M -dimensional space into regions and provide the decoder with a metric for each region. The metric information is also an M -dimensional vector whose M components are the metrics assigned to each of the M hypothesized transmitted signals. Metric information from the quantizer is provided to the decoder. The decoder searches for codewords (for block codes) or paths (for convolutional codes) which yields the best metric.

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Fig. 1 — System diagram

Figure 2 shows the specific demodulator-quantizer structure used in this study. This diagram depicts typical elements of the M energy detectors matched to the M candidate tones. (For analytical convenience the square root of the energy output is used instead of the energy itself.) Each demodulator output is presented to a quantizer-limiter which classifies the output into one of N regions. (The case of $N = 4$ is used in this study.) The quantizer output levels are arbitrarily labeled $0, 1, \dots, N - 1$. These are not the decoder metrics themselves, but they do tell which metric value should be used. (This is discussed in the next section.) Each of the tone filter quantizers has N possible outputs so that the bank of M filters has N^M possible M -vector outputs. The coding channel shown in Fig. 1 has M possible inputs and N^M possible outputs with each output having M scalar components.

ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE AND RESULTS

Our goal here is to find the cutoff rate parameter R_0 (bits/channel use) which represents the maximum data rate that is practically achievable. For an M -ary orthogonal alphabet on a memoryless channel, R_0 can be written as

$$R_0 = \log_2 M - \log_2 [1 + (M - 1)D], \quad (1)$$

where D is the pairwise Chernoff upper bound on the probability that the metric of an incorrect signal exceeds the metric of the sent signal. For any specific code, it is possible to upper bound the decoded P_b by a function purely of D , that is,

$$P_b \leq B(D). \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2) the function B depends on the specific code used and the Chernoff bound D depends solely on the coding channel as

Fig. 2 — The quantizer-limiter receiver structure

shown in Fig. 1. This technique of decoupling the code and the coding channel was suggested by Omura and Levitt [2].

Avidor [3] derived D for a partial band Gaussian interference channel with FH/MFSK and a quantizer-limiter. In Ref. 3, the results were applied to a Rayleigh fading channel, a case for which the worst-case partial band interference happens to be full-band interference. In our study, we apply the expression for D to the nonfading case so that the worst-case interference fraction must be determined.

Before considering Avidor's results, it is useful to define several probabilities that are associated with the quantizer-limiter. Let z and z' be outputs of the tone filter corresponding to the sent signal and one of the $M - 1$ tone filters with signal absent, respectively. (The subscripts of the z 's as shown in Fig. 2 are deleted here to simplify the notation.) We define an interference indicator random variable I by letting $I = 1$ if the transmission hopping subband has interference and by letting $I = 0$ if it is interference free. The probability density functions (pdf's) of z and z' , conditioned on the on-off state of the interference, are

$$p(z | I = 1) = \frac{2z}{N_0/\rho} \exp\left[-\frac{(z^2 + E_S)}{N_0/\rho}\right] I_0\left(\frac{2z\sqrt{E_S}}{N_0/\rho}\right), \quad (3a)$$

$$p(z' | I = 1) = \frac{2z'}{N_0/\rho} \exp\left[-\frac{z'^2}{N_0/\rho}\right], \quad (3b)$$

$$p(z | I = 0) = \delta(z - \sqrt{E_S}), \quad (3c)$$

$$p(z' | I = 0) = \delta(z'), \quad (3d)$$

where N_0 is the average power spectral density over the entire hopping band, N_0/ρ is the power spectral density in the portion of the hopping band with interference, and E_S is the energy per transmitted MFSK tone symbol. In Eq. (3a) we have a Ricean pdf where $I_0(\cdot)$ is the zero-order modified Bessel function. In Eq. (3b) we have a Rayleigh pdf. In Eqs. (3c) and (3d), $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function.

For the Ricean and Rayleigh pdf's in Eqs. (3a) and (3b), the Marcum Q -function gives the area to the right of a threshold value on a normalized pdf. This is defined by

$$Q(a, b) = \int_b^\infty u \exp\left[-\frac{(u^2 + a^2)}{2}\right] I_0(au) du. \quad (4)$$

The special case (Rayleigh pdf) where $a = 0$ yields the simple expression

$$Q(0, b) = \int_b^\infty u \exp\left[-\frac{u^2}{2}\right] du = \exp\left[-\frac{b^2}{2}\right]. \quad (5)$$

With this background, we return to the quantizer-limiter shown in Fig. 2. The threshold settings are at jT ; $j = 0, 1, 2, 3$. For ease of implementation, we arbitrarily choose $T = \sqrt{N_0}$. (This assumes that we are able to measure an average power spectral density N_0 over the entire hopping band.) The corresponding four possible quantizer output levels are taken as the integers j where $j = 0, 1, 2, 3$. We also use j to indicate a quantizer input region, with region j corresponding to a quantizer input between jT and $(j + 1)T$ which produces an output j .

We define the conditional probabilities $P_m^j(I)$; $j = 0, 1, 2, 3$; $m = 0, 1$; $I = 0, 1$; so that j indicates the quantizer region, m indicates the correct or incorrect tone filter (where $m = 1$ refers to the correct filter and $m = 0$ refers to an incorrect filter), and I is the interference indicator. For example, $P_1^2(1)$ is the probability that the output of the quantizer of the correct tone filter is 2 given that interference is present. These conditional probabilities can be written by using Eqs. (3), (4), and (5) as

$$P_1^j(1) = Q[\sqrt{2\rho E_S}/N_0, j\sqrt{2\rho}] - Q[\sqrt{2\rho E_S}/N_0, (j + 1)\sqrt{2\rho}]; \\ j = 0, 1, 2;$$

$$P_1^3(1) = Q[\sqrt{2\rho E_S}/N_0, 3\sqrt{2\rho}],$$

$$P_0^j(1) = \exp[-j^2\rho] - \exp[-(j + 1)^2\rho]; \quad j = 0, 1, 2;$$

$$P_0^3(1) = \exp[-9\rho],$$

$$P_1^j(0) = \begin{cases} 1; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} j^2 < E_S/N_0 \leq (j + 1)^2; \quad j = 0, 1, 2; \\ j^2 < E_S/N_0; \quad j = 3 \end{array} \right. \\ 0; & \text{other} \end{cases}$$

$$P_0^j(0) = \begin{cases} 1; & j = 0 \\ 0; & j = 1, 2, 3. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

From the conditional probabilities in Eqs. (6) we can write the total (unconditional) probabilities of the quantizer output being j for the correct and incorrect tone filters, respectively as

$$P_1^j = \rho P_1^j(1) + (1 - \rho)P_1^j(0); \quad j = 0, 1, 2, 3; \quad (7a)$$

and

$$P_0^j = \rho P_0^j(1) + (1 - \rho)P_0^j(0); \quad j = 0, 1, 2, 3. \quad (7b)$$

Avidor [3] derived the expression for D to be used in Eq. (1), and it is given by

$$D = \min_{\lambda > 0} \max_{0 < \rho \leq 1} \left\{ (1 - \rho) \sum_{j=0}^3 P_0^j(0) \left[\frac{P_1^j}{P_0^j} \right]^\lambda \sum_{j=0}^3 P_1^j(0) \left[\frac{P_0^j}{P_1^j} \right]^\lambda \right. \\ \left. + \rho \sum_{j=0}^3 P_0^j(1) \left[\frac{P_1^j}{P_0^j} \right]^\lambda \sum_{j=0}^3 P_1^j(1) \left[\frac{P_0^j}{P_1^j} \right]^\lambda \right\}. \quad (8)$$

We may evaluate D as a function of E_S/N_0 by using Eqs. (6) and (7) in Eq. (8) and performing a simultaneous maximization over ρ and minimization over λ . With this result for D , we return to Eq. (1) to evaluate R_0 as a function of E_S/N_0 . Figures 3 to 7 give the curves for R_0 for five alphabet sizes ($M = 2, 4, 8, 16$, and 32). For comparison purposes, we also show the corresponding results for a pure soft decision receiver with perfect side information and for a hard decision receiver. We see that in all cases of interest, the quantizer-limiter gives results within about 2 dB of the perfect

Fig. 3 — R_0 vs E_S/N_0 for alphabet size $M = 2$

Fig. 4 — R_0 vs E_s/N_0 for alphabet size $M = 4$

Fig. 6 — R_0 vs E_s/N_0 for alphabet size $M = 16$

Fig. 5 — R_0 vs E_s/N_0 for alphabet size $M = 8$

Fig. 7 — R_0 vs E_s/N_0 for alphabet size $M = 32$

soft decision receiver assisted by perfect side information. Figure 8 shows the worst-case interference fraction ρ as a function of E_s/N_0 .

Although the quantizer-limiter output levels are designated as j , where $j = 0, 1, 2$, or 3 , Avidor [3] gives the actual metric $m(j)$ used by the decoder when the quantizer-limiter output is j as the log-likelihood metric

$$m(j) = \ln \frac{P_1^j}{P_0^j} \quad (9)$$

To achieve performance close to the theoretical performance, the receiver must have enough long-term channel state information to be able to approximate the metric given in Eq. (9). In practice, this is not difficult to do.

With the R_0 result, it is useful to plot E_s/N_0 versus the code rate R when the code rate is equal to the cutoff rate normalized to channel bits instead of channel symbols. Since there are $\log_2 M$ channel bits per channel symbol, the code rate (at cutoff) is defined as

$$R = \frac{R_0}{\log_2 M} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 8 — Worst-case interference fraction ρ vs E_s/N_0 (all alphabet sizes)

and it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_b}{N_0} &= \frac{1}{R \log_2 M} \frac{E_S}{N_0} \\ &= \frac{1}{R_0} \frac{E_S}{N_0} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Figures 9 to 13 are curves of E_b/N_0 versus R for the quantizer-limiter on a worst-case partial band interference channel for $M = 2, 4, 8, 16,$ and 32 . These are compared to the hard decision receiver and the ideal soft decision receiver with perfect side information.

The performance of a specific code for the coding channel in question can be derived from the R_0 versus E_S/N_0 curves by using the curve translation principle of Omura and Levitt [2]. As an example of curve translation, we consider the $K = 7, R = 1/2$ binary convolutional code. The P_b versus E_b/N_0 results are well known for the hard decision channel and the soft decision (with side information) channel. From the R_0 versus

Fig. 9 — E_b/N_0 vs R for code rate at cutoff. $M = 2$

Fig. 10 — E_b/N_0 vs R for code rate at cutoff. $M = 4$

Fig. 11 — E_b/N_0 vs R for code rate at cutoff. $M = 8$

Fig. 12 — E_b/N_0 vs R for code rate at cutoff. $M = 16$

Fig. 13 — E_b/N_0 vs R for code rate at cutoff. $M = 32$

E_s/N_0 curves in Fig. 3, we are able to perform curve translation on either the hard decision or soft decision curves to get the P_b versus E_b/N_0 curve for this code on the quantizer-limiter coding channel. Figure 14 shows this result along with the hard and soft decision results. We see that for $P_b = 10^{-5}$ the improvement is 5 dB over hard decision decoding and is within 1.4 dB of the ideal soft decision result.

CONCLUSIONS

The large performance difference between ideal soft decision receivers and practical hard decision receivers on a worst-case partial band Gaussian interference channel has become evident in recent studies. This has stimulated interest in a search for implementable high-performance soft decision quantization receivers. The Q-L receiver described in this report satisfies this simultaneous requirement for robust performance and practical realizability.

The Q-L receiver described here is nonadaptive, and fixed threshold settings are based upon long-term measurements of the average noise background. Future studies might be directed at further optimizing the number and location of the threshold settings. Also, other interference types need to be considered, for example, worst-case tone interference. For this disturbance, the performance difference from the ideal soft decision to hard decision

is greater than for partial band Gaussian interference, so it would be of interest to see if the Q-L receiver reduces this gap as effectively for tone interference as it does for partial band Gaussian interference.

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REFERENCES

1. A. J. Viterbi and I. M. Jacobs, "Advances in Coding and Modulation for Noncoherent Channels Affected by Fading, Partial-Band and Multiple-Access Interference," in *Advances in Communication Systems* (New York, Academic Press, 1975), Vol. 4.
2. J. K. Omura and B. K. Levitt, "Coded Error Probability Evaluation for Antijam Communication Systems," *IEEE Trans. Comm. Com-30* (5), 896-903 (1982).
3. D. Avidor, "Antijam Analysis of Frequency Hopping M-ary Frequency Shift Keying Communication Systems in High Frequency Rayleigh Fading Channels," PhD Dissertation, System Science Department, UCLA, June 1981.

Fig. 14 — P_b vs E_b/N_0 for $K = 7$, $R = 1/2$ binary code